
ANALYSIS AND DEGREE OF COMPLEXITY OF TEACHING ARCHITECTURAL TERMS

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ABSTRACT

This article describes most used architectural words with specialized texts. The intention of this research is to inspire a discussion about the changes in architecture terminology with the revolution in communication and representation forms as a result of digitalisation. Research on technical vocabulary has shown a significant underestimation of the role played by technical vocabulary in specialized texts and lack of information about how technical vocabulary relates to other types of vocabulary. Also in this article has shown a study of the technical vocabulary in an architecture text and the technical vocabulary in an applied linguistics texts

Keywords: *technical, vocabulary, specialized, terminology, terms ,civil engineering, architecture, field.*

Over the course of centuries, architects and builders have developed specialized terms to describe their buildings. Also we should pay more attention groups of terms which deals to historical Uzbek monuments.

The intention of this research is to inspire a discussion about the changes in architecture terminology with the revolution in communication and representation forms as a result of digitalisation.

The blurred boundary between the virtual and the analogue worlds, the misunderstandings and the confusion that appear with the interaction of these two worlds nowadays form the major problems facing architectural design, education and research. The researchers in this field are focused on the interface, the meeting and the transformation point between the digital and analogue worlds in order to prevent those problems and confusions. One of the main reasons of this ambiguity is the architectural terminology that changes according to the changing status of architectural representation i.e. new forms of representation; new forms of communication i.e. the new role of the architect and the researcher. As architecture

terminology is essential to improve today's challenging, multidisciplinary communication in order to clarify the problems of ambiguity and unawareness (as a result of shift of specific architectural vocabulary) it is necessary to analyse the changes in the architectural terminology which will form the discussion point of the following paper.

There are specific difficulties in learning foreign languages, as is every other field. Due to in every specialty has its own history, its present and future. Without knowing the history of the subject or science that is being studied, it is difficult to understand the current day or to develop ideas for its further development. Likewise, the student who is studying this field must know the same terminologies or specific words according to this subject as foreign languages. Today's development in the highly developed century is not limited that every one of us perfectly well in his sphere, but also should speak in several foreign languages exactly.

To ensure the successful development and enhancement of the state in all spheres, existing and every growing cadre must meet the world standards and be competitive. For this reason the reforms in our country pays great attention to the training of qualified personnel. The Republic of Uzbekistan adopted the National Training Program on August 29, 1997 in the years of independence. The program envisages radical reforming of education system in Uzbekistan, improving the quality of education and improving the system of continuous education.

Provider has been producing mature competitive specialists .

Every expert should be able to comprehend his knowledge of his or her knowledge of foreign languages and compete with the world experience.

Each industry has its own terms. Especially when the technology industry is rapidly developing, knowing the technological terms is not an exaggeration to every specialist who works in this field. There are a lot of these terms in the field of developing construction. In the course of construction in our country, every engineer and architects who have grown up a great deal of attention to the study of foreign languages.

Our country is cooperating with many countries in the sphere of housing construction and road construction. In a word, our country is becoming more and more beautiful in our unique home country. For this purpose, the use of innovative methods in the field of excellent teaching of foreign languages in the higher education institutions in the field of construction, and familiarization with industry-related words has become a topical issue. Developing engineers have their own

construction materials, products, and designs that are specific to their processes and events, the properties of the materials and their composition, and the processes that take place in the whole process. For example: technological processes in the production of building materials, the boundaries and brands of finished products, the classification of materials, their deformities properties, the theology and, of course, the characteristics of each material.

The ability to speak English with these terms is the result of every engineer's engineer. However, learning and applying field-specific terminology is an urgent matter for every expert. There are several easy ways to teach terminology in English. The most convenient and popular method is interactive and graphic organs. Today's 21st Century while technology is rapidly developing, it is important to use innovative technology in every area of education. Innovation in the field of technology, in many economic, social and humanitarian spheres is rapidly developing. The word "Innovation" (English - Innovation) comes from the word innovation, which means novelty. In order to benefit from the wide use of innovation, it is important to know foreign languages to share experiences with foreign countries and to be competitive with them.

For this purpose, the attention paid to the foreign language is high in our country. Every educational institution provides qualified staff and learning opportunities for learning foreign languages. In particular, in order to radically revise the content of cadres training in accordance with the priorities of the country 's socio - economic development and to create the necessary conditions for the training of highly qualified specialists as a result of international standards, the PAC - 2909, On Measures for Development ". This resolution envisages a qualitative improvement and improvement of the level of higher education; strengthening the material and technical basis of higher education institutions, and the program of comprehensive development of the higher education system for 2017-2021 for the wide application of innovative technologies. At present, innovation in the development of education has led to an important field of pedagogical education. The term "Innovative Pedagogy" and its research into western Europe and the USA appeared in the 60s of the XX century. Innovative activity was investigated by F.N.Gonobolin, S.M.Godnin, V.Konkalik, N.V.Kuzmina.

Pedagogical literature contains a scheme of innovation, which includes the following steps:

1. A new idea or a new concept to apply;

2. Innovation;
3. Stage of practical application of the created innovation;
4. Broadcasting innovation phase;
5. The rule of innovation in a particular area; [4]

Innovative technology is widely used especially in teaching foreign languages. Comparison of the learned language and mother tongue to learn the language quickly and easily is the most important method for learning the similar and contexts. Innovative technology covers several interactive methods, such as: intelligence, method of inquiry, analysis and synthesis. Innovative educational technologies have the following theoretical foundations: methodological, historical, philosophical, economic, legal, normative, psychological, pedagogical, deductive, social. Nowadays, interest in and interest in applying interactive methods, innovative technologies and pedagogical learning is increasing day by day, one of the reasons for this is that while traditional teaching students are taught to acquire only the knowledge they need, analyze, even make conclusions themselves.

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